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Mobile Learning in Saudi Arabia

I. Context

Using the location and situation as the context (Brown, 2010) in the kingdom, Islamic norms are strictly adhered and gender segregation from all levels of education must be observed. This context of location will enable learners to interact seamlessly online without any physical contact from both genders. The ubiquity of mobile devices enables higher education learners to participate in educational activities without fear of being caught mixing with opposite gender.

II. Challenges and issues

One of the key issues that Saudi students found in implementing m-learning is the high internet fees (Al-Shehri, 2013). Living in Saudi Arabia now, mobile internet has become more expensive than Fibr or home internet connection. There is no unlimited subscription for mobile internet-browsing usage but rather mostly unlimited social media usage. Mobile internet browsing subscription starts from 40 USD (150 SAR) for a 10 GB plan with unlimited social networking. If using mobile learning all the time, 10 GB won't be enough for a month of mobile usage. There is unlimited subscription which starts from 90 USD per month. So, even university students are given monthly stipend (1,000 SAR) by the government by simply studying, this fee might be just an added burden to them.

Another challenge that is pressing in Saudi Arabia's mobile internet learning is, the connectivity itself. KSA is 2.15 million km² which makes it difficult for the telecommunication companies to provide stable and efficient connections, especially in the rural areas (Al-Shehri, 2013). There are still parts of the kingdom where mobile internet connection is either weak or not existent.

Ultra-conservative tradition in the kingdom (Al-Marwani, 2011) is also identified as one of the issues. All educational programs that will go through to the system must pass through to the government agencies and religious authorities making learning less open and controlled.

III. Teaching and learning activities involved

While there is a wide mobile subscription in Saudi Arabia, the use of mobile devices for educational purposes is rather limited. Mostly, it's only used for file sharing and communication. There is lack of studies and standardization about the mobile phone usage at larger scale throughout the kingdom. (Al-Masarweh, 2018). One of the 25 public universities, King Saud University has adopted m-learning in their system but only offering opportunity to send messages (SMS) to individuals or group via PC only allowing the school authorities to manage the feature (Al-Mutairy, et.al, 2015).

In addition, a study conducted by Al-Masarweh of King Abdulaziz University, Jeddah (2018) to Saudi Arabian universities' faculty members, he found out that most of the concerns of these people are about the management of the learning program and the operations. Among the six (6) concern categories stated, the results went to the stage three (3) or the Task concern stage stated above.

IV. Mobile technology used

Right now, there is no existing m-learning initiative by the Saudi government. Universities are taking initiatives to start this method if applicable. Mostly of the focus is on e-learning and distance learning (Al Harthi, 2018).

According to Al-Shehri (2013), the future of mobile learning in the kingdom is through mobile social. And I agree with it, as reported by Arab News, Saudi Arabia ranks 3rd globally for the smartphone use with 72.8% of the total population are users. Instant messaging or IMs like WhatsApp or BlackBerry Messenger are common among Saudis because they can share opinions, news, and information through it faster and without having to worry about being caught by authorities.

V. Participants

Participants in the studies are students and professors from various Saudi universities and Saudi university students studying abroad.

VI. Resources needed

Right now, the kingdom has established an organization that is directly linked with the ministry of education. The National Center for e-Learning ([NCeL](#)) is in-charge for all aspects related to e-learning and distance education. According to the Saudi government [website](#), these are the responsibilities of NCeL:

- Setting regulations and quality standards of e-Learning.
- Control the quality of e-Learning programs.
- Grant licenses for companies and governmental entities of e-learning programs to provide accredited certificates.
- Qualifying for the licenses granted to the entities and companies providing e-learning programs.
- Supervision of the Open Educational Resources program OER.
- Conducting research and studies in the field of e-learning.
- Provide consultancy services in e-Learning.
- Organizing conferences, meetings and workshops.
- Represent Saudi Arabia abroad in the field of e-Learning.

In this case, universities couldn't just start an m-learning system without the approval from this entity. As mentioned, the government must have the control of everything especially when dealing with educational content, especially on e-learning.

VII. What has worked well

Using the UTAUT (unified theory of acceptance and use of technology) model of research conducted by Baldewan, A., et. al. (2016) higher education Saudi students showed positive enthusiasm to utilize m-Learning as mode of learning in their universities.

In addition, universities in the kingdom are exerting effort to integrate innovation such as m-learning to help them advance the use of distance learning in general (Baldewan, A., et. al, 2016).

In the same study, in terms of the tech use, the students prefer more the use of iPads or tablets which gets the higher percentage rate among 400 participants, giving way to the designers to develop applications which are compatible to this technology.

VIII. What could have been done differently

Students and faculty members of Saudi Arabian universities are willing to adapt to this mobile learning environment provided that they will have a good support from stakeholders.

In a study conducted by Chanchary, F. H. and Islam, S. (2011) at Najran Univeristy, students have a welcoming attitude towards this change and they like the flexibility and availability of information is easier between and among learners and teachers. On the other hand, still large number of students have got no idea what is m-learning all about. Nevertheless, they still show interest in the blended learning form that will be included in their class lectures.

IX. Recommendation

Mentioning the location as the context (Brown, 2010) Saudi Arabia is a vast landscape of desert and mountains, universities can be far from cities or rural villages where students live. Mobile technology could ease this plight of learners to get a bachelor's degree. I had a student before who was taking his BA in a university which is more than 200 km away from his home however distance and e-learning enabled him to continue his studies without going to the physical school every day.

In the mentioned challenges, one of the factors that affects m-learning is the expensive internet subscription. Since, Saudi government has the control of everything, I may recommend have a directive to telecommunications companies to make special internet offers to higher education students currently enrolled in a university. I think it would be possible since the government has all the access to its universities.

In addition, telecommunication companies should expedite the building of cell-sites to widen their coverage within the kingdom. This will enable more rural villages to get connected and have chance to enroll in universities without going far from home.

Using mobile devices will help learners (both genders) to interact and learn without the fear of being caught by authorities as physical contact among opposite genders are strictly prohibited in the kingdom.

For universities willing to adopt the method of learning, a careful study has to be conducted first before the implementation of the program to avoid backlash. And also programs must go through first the authorities to get approved if these are aligned to Islamic norms and traditions of the kingdom.

The government continues to send scholars abroad to get more ideas on education. One of the goals of KSA is to build a knowledge-based economy and by doing this they are on the good track. Integration of m-learning among public and private universities will give an inclusive education to all income levels of Saudi families.

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